
IMPACT OF TAX E-FILLING SYSTEMS AND E-PAYMENT PLATFORMS ON REVENUE GENERATION IN NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This paper investigates the impact of Tax e-Filing Systems and e-Payment Platforms on Revenue Generation in Niger State, Nigeria. It adopts a quantitative cross-sectional survey research design *via the use of structured questionnaire administered on the* 156 senior management staff of the Niger State Internal Revenue Service (NSIRS). The data collected from the administered questionnaires were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics to achieve the study's stated objectives. Descriptive statistics and diagnostic tests were employed to summarize and evaluate the dataset for both the dependent and independent variables through measures such as mean, median, maximum, minimum values, standard deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis. For inferential statistics, Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was applied using SPSS to test the research hypotheses. The findings derived from the results shows that despite its potential benefits, electronic filing does not significantly contribute to revenue generation. The study concludes that increasing adoption through public education, technical improvements, and incentives for digital filing will help improve its effectiveness. In addition, the study confirms that electronic payment is critical for tax revenue generation and shows that ensuring a secure and efficient e-payment system will encourage taxpayer compliance, reduce fraud, and streamline revenue collection processes. The paper recommends that NSIRS should provide adequate technical support to assist taxpayers in navigating the e-filing process. Furthermore, continuous monitoring and system upgrades should be implemented to improve reliability and efficiency. The government should collaborate with financial institutions to expand access to electronic payment platforms in both urban and rural areas. Finally, the paper recommends that stakeholders should direct investments toward improving internet infrastructure, especially in remote areas, to ensure seamless access to digital tax platforms

Keywords: Tax e-Filing Systems, e-Payment Platforms, Revenue Generation, Niger State Internal Revenue Service (NSIRS), Niger State, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Revenue generation is a critical component of economic stability and growth for nations worldwide. It serves as the primary source of funding for public services, infrastructure development, healthcare, education, and other essential government functions (Mose, Tanchev & Fumey, 2024). Effective revenue generation enables governments to reduce reliance on external borrowing, stabilize economies, and promote sustainable development (Bird & Zolt, 2008). Globally, nations strive to optimize revenue collection to meet the increasing demands of their populations and address socio-economic challenges (Mascagni, Moore & McCluskey, 2014). For instance,

developed countries like the United States and members of the European Union, have leveraged advanced tax systems to achieve high revenue-to-GDP ratios, which support robust public services and economic resilience (OECD, 2020).

In Nigeria, revenue generation has been a persistent challenge because of overreliance on oil exports, weak tax compliance, and inefficiencies in tax administration (Adeyeye, Oyekunle, Adeyeye & Korubo, 2022). According to the World Bank (2022), Nigeria's tax-to-GDP ratio is one of the lowest in the world at approximately 6%, which is significantly below the African average of 16.5%. This low revenue generation capacity has constrained the government's ability to fund critical infrastructure and social services, worsening poverty and inequality (Adegbie & Fakile, 2020). Niger State, like many other states in Nigeria, faces similar challenges. With its predominantly agrarian economy and limited industrial base, the state struggles to generate sufficient internal revenue to meet its developmental needs. The Niger State Internal Revenue Service (NSIRS) has reported that over 70% of the state's revenue comes from federal allocations, making it vulnerable to fluctuations in oil prices and federal revenue sharing (NSIRS, 2021).

In recent times, marked by unprecedented crises, governments worldwide have been grappling with the need for substantial resources to implement critical policies. This urgency has sparked debates on tax reforms, ranging between increasing existing taxes and introducing new ones. However, an innovative perspective is gaining traction, focusing on harnessing the potential of information and communication technologies (ICT) to enhance tax collection efficiency, thereby reducing the risks of tax evasion and reporting errors. This approach, which leverages ICT to reduce compliance costs and streamline tax collection, is at the core of modern e-government initiatives aimed at augmenting service delivery and operational efficiency.

In the last decade, the public sector has undergone a transformative journey marked by a persistent pursuit to enhance service delivery while trimming administrative costs. The strategic integration of technology has significantly driven this transformation which has played a pivotal role in refining procedures and ensuring robust accountability and transparency. This digital revolution reshapes how governments interact with citizens, particularly in terms of public financial management and taxation. At the heart of a state's financial well-being is its tax system—a vital source of income that must continually adapt to the ever-evolving technological and economic landscape.

In recent years, digitalization has emerged as a transformative tool for improving tax administration and revenue generation. Digitalization involves the integration of digital technologies into tax processes, such as e-filing, e-payment, automated compliance checks, and data analytics. These technologies enhance efficiency, reduce administrative costs, and improve transparency, thereby increasing tax compliance and revenue collection (Fjeldstad & Heggstad, 2012). Countries like Estonia and Rwanda have demonstrated the potential of digital tax systems to significantly boost revenue generation and reduce tax evasion (IMF, 2021).

In Nigeria, the federal government and some states have begun to adopt digital tax administration systems to address revenue collection inefficiencies. The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) introduced the Integrated Tax Administration System (ITAS) to automate tax processes and improve compliance (FIRS, 2020).

Niger State, despite its potential for agricultural and mineral resources, has struggled to optimize its revenue generation because of outdated tax administration systems. The state's reliance on manual processes has led to inefficiencies, corruption, and low taxpayer compliance (NSIRS, 2021). Recognizing the need for reform, the Niger State government has expressed interest in adopting digital technologies to modernize its tax administration system. However, the impact of such digitalization efforts on revenue generation in the state remains understudied.

In Niger state, Nigeria inefficiencies have plagued tax administration practices and performance, resulting in significant revenue losses. The NGIRS faces challenges in tax collection, recording a low tax-to-GDP ratio of 6.3% in 2023 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). This percentage is significantly lower than the OECD average of 34.3% (OECD, 2023).

In Niger State, manual tax filing and payment processes dominate, leading to high compliance costs for taxpayers, inefficient tax collection and remittance, and limited tax data and analytics for informed decision-making (FIRS, 2022; NGIRS, 2023; World Bank, 2024).

In addition, there is inadequate empirical research on specific tax administration challenges in Niger State. Only a handful of studies, such as Yusuf, 2020, studied the impact of manual processes, limited tax payer registration, and inadequate infrastructure on tax compliance and revenue collection in Niger state.

This study seeks to provide practical answers to two raised questions: how does the adoption of e-filing systems influence overall revenue generation in Niger State? How do e-payment platforms affect the accuracy and timeliness of revenue collection in Niger State?

The study on the impact of digitalization on tax administration practices and performance in the Niger State Internal Revenue Service is significant because it will contribute to the scarce literature on digitalization in tax administration in Nigeria, providing valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners. By investigating the impact of digitalization on tax administration in Niger state, the study will aim to contribute to the advancement of knowledge, policy and practice in this critical area. This will inform strategies for improving tax revenue collection, compliance, and data management in Niger State and other similar contexts. The effectiveness of digitalization to enhance tax administration efficiency and identify areas for improvement. This will provide a framework for assessing the impact of digitalization on tax administration, applicable to other African countries facing similar challenges. This study will also shed light on the challenges and opportunities of digitalization in tax administration, guiding future research and development in this area.

The findings of this study have practical implications for enhancing tax revenue generation in the Niger state, improving tax compliance and reducing evasion, strengthening tax administration efficiency and effectiveness, and informing policy decisions on digitalization in tax administration in Nigeria and beyond.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Literature Review

Electronic Tax filing system

According to Mumonge (2011), Electronic tax filing, or e-filing, is a system for electronically submitting tax documents to a revenue service, often without the need to submit any paper documents. Electronic tax filing systems are e-government applications used with increasing frequency worldwide. The Federal Inland Revenue

Service (FIRS) of Nigeria embarked on an Integrated Tax Administration System (ITAS) project in 2013. The ITAS aims to enhance tax administration and simplify the tax compliance process in Nigeria by using technology.

Electronic Tax Identification Number

The digitalization process started with what is termed a “modernization project,” in which the service started leveraging on information technology to standardized its operations, such as automation of tax filling and collection that curtailed corruption, increase monitoring and tracking capabilities FIRS (Bennet, 2012). This laid the foundation of the digitalization process (Premium Times, 2020).

Electronic Filing of Tax Returns on Performance

Digital technologies can strengthen tax administration and enhance domestic revenue mobilization; such mobilization has been a long-standing challenge (particularly in developing countries) in scaling up priority social and infrastructure spending. Over the past few decades, tax administrations have adopted new technologies to enhance the effectiveness of tax collection, yet they have also introduced new challenges (Gupta, Jalles & Liu, 2022).

E-Tax Payment and Revenue Generation

The need for tax payments has been a phenomenon of global significance because it affects every economy, irrespective of national differences. Tax payment is not for the direct exchange of good and/or services but a transfer of resources and income from the private sector to the public sector in order to achieve some of the nation’s economic and social goals (Nnubia, et al., 2020).

2.2.6 Electronic Tax Clearance Certificate (e-TCC)

The e-filing system is the Electronic Tax Clearance Certificate (e-TCC) processing. Taxpayers can apply for a TCC online, which will be generated by the system. Although hard copies will still be available for collection. A system-generated TCC will be just as tenable as a hard copy. Either way, the software allows for TCC verification by third parties online using the TCC number (Chiu, 2019).

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

The study’s conceptual framework is as follows:

Source: Study's Conceptual Review (2025)

Theoretical Framework

The digitalization of tax administration can be understood through the lens of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Institutional Theory. TAM suggests that taxpayers and tax authorities will accept and use digital tax systems if they perceive them as useful and easy to use, which will improve tax compliance and revenue collection (Mishra et al., 2023). For instance, Nieria's adoption of an electronic tax system led to increased revenue collection and improved taxpayer flexibility (Okafor et al., 2020). Institutional Theory explains how external factors, such as government policies and social norms, influence digitalization adoption in the tax system (Asongu & Ofori, 2022), shaping the institutional framework that supports tax collection. For example, a study on tax revenue mobilization in sub-Saharan Africa found that institutional quality and political stability are crucial factors in effective tax collection (Koh et al., 2022).

Together, these two theories support the current study by highlighting the importance of user acceptance, technological design, and institutional support in shaping the successful implementation of digital tax systems, which is critical for domestic revenue mobilization in Niger state, Nigeria.

Empirical review

Digitalization of revenue can be defined as a process through which governments use information communication and technologies to obtain more accurate and timely information about revenue operations. In addition, this new tax system e-governance tool improves service delivery by reducing the time and cost of tax declarations to citizens. Moreover, these manual tax systems promote corruption through the frequency of in-person interactions between taxpayers and tax collectors (Adeleye, N., & Eboagu, C. 2019).

During the first phase, digital strategic capabilities were built through several processes, such as the definition of the new vision that guided the organization transformation during the last decade, the review of the organization's mission, and the formulation and deployment of the strategy (Aslam, Delepierre, & Gupta, 2022). According to (Rogan, 2022), a multiple regression approach under the generalized method of moments, the author showed that digitalization has positive effects on tax revenues over the study period 1980-2017. His findings indicate that financial development, human resource quality, and industrialization are the main channels through which digitalization impacts tax revenue collection.

The telecommunication service in the telecommunication sector is made up of companies that make digital services possible on a global scale, whether through the phone or the internet, through airwaves or cables, through wires, or wirelessly. These companies created an infrastructure that allows data in words, voice, audio, or video to be sent anywhere in the world. The largest companies in this sector are telephone (both wired and wireless) operators, satellite companies, cable companies, and internet service providers. The main goal of these digitalization policies is to improve tax revenue collection by taking advantage of the increasing rate of ICT penetration in the region (Myovella, G., Karacuka, M., & Haucap, J. 2023).

Bate (2021) recommended taxation as a means by which governments supply public goods and services and act as a compulsory fee. It is a major part of the economy, and the legislature of a nation cannot do anything without collecting tax revenues from citizens. Taxation assumes an imperative job of improving the economy in a nation. This helps the presence of the nation and its nonfinancial independence and allows the authority to support social welfare projects and framework activities in the country. It equally distributes wealth, allocates resources fairly, eradicates foreign dependency, and keeps the domestic industry from external industrialists by restricting imports through heavy taxes.

In developing countries, digital revenue represents a much higher percentage of national output than in developed countries. Similarly, more national output is channeled to governmental use through taxation in developing countries with the highest levels of income than in those with lesser incomes. Certainly, in many respects, the tax systems of the developing countries with the highest levels of income have more in common with those of developed countries than they have with the tax systems of the poorest developing countries (Bate 2021). The digital economy generates new business, which, in turn, increases the country's tax base. Second, the digital economy improves tax compliance by providing better information to the tax authority on the identification of individuals and economic activities, such as bank transactions and interest income of the private sector (Bate 2021). Thus, this information enhances the ability of tax administration to collect and disseminate tax timeliars. Third, the digital economy increases tax administration efficiency, implying more cost reductions in tax collection and inspection. Finally, the digital economy allows for e-governance by reducing the cost of administrative procedures to citizens. Hence, digitalization improves public service delivery, which, in turn, motivates citizens to be good taxpayers (Adeleye, N., & Eboagu, C. 2019).

Countries in Sub-Saharan Africa began to implement digitalization policies of tax systems in the early 2000s. The main goal of these digitalization policies is to improve tax revenues collection by taking advantage of the increasing rate of ICTs penetration in the region. Obviously, the digitalization of tax collection systems in Africa is very recent and less documented due to limited cases of experience (Kenani, J. M., Masiya, M., & Njolomole, M. S. 2021b).

Many authors also support the positive effects of the digital economy on tax revenues (Gupta et al., 2017; Ndung'u, 2017). In this study, we develop a conceptual model that conceptualizes channels through which digital revenue on the economy could affect revenues mobilization telecommunications carriers; communications hardware, and satellite and telecommunication resellers. Gupta et al., (2017) acknowledged that the telecom industry involved in the provision of national networks across the world is increasingly targeted by hackers, exposing various security issues. The hackers' main aim is to steal valuable information and use it in their own

favor. Despite various measures taken by many national governments resorting to stricter regulatory norms for foreign hardware manufacturers, issues concerning national security continue to rise.

The fundamental role of tax administrations across the globe is to raise tax revenues according to existing tax laws. An effective tax system is crucial for both developing and developed countries because adequate revenue collection is an important determinant of economic growth (Matthews, 2011; Arnold et al., 2021; Akgun, Cournède, & Fournier, 2017) and is highly connected to firms' performance (Dabla-Norris et al., 2017; Bergner et al., 2017). Empirically, Oseni (2021) deduced that tax evaders will no longer have loopholes to hide with the usage of the modern automated tax technology and systems because all taxpayers have to make use of the tax system to declare all their transactions. Moreover, in the case of developing countries, an effective tax system is also a decisive contributor to successful state-building (Fjeldstad & Moore, 2009). Three paradigms stand out as the most widely shared models for tax authorities across the globe in recent times: the enforcement paradigm, the service (or facilitation) paradigm, and the trust paradigm (Alm, 2014; Prichard et al., 2019). The first and most traditional enforcement approach prioritizes auditing and "catch and punish" activities, while the second places more weight on facilitating compliance through better information and lower compliance costs, sometimes overlapping with the third, in which emphasis is placed on building citizens' trust in the system to reinforce voluntary compliance. All these paradigms have their own benefits and drawbacks, and they are frequently best used in combination to significantly contribute to more efficient collections and overall higher compliance levels. This has been confirmed in recent empirical studies and laboratory experiments (Alm, 2014; Kasper & Alm, 2022).

Ultimately, "tax administration is tax policy" (de Jantscher, 1992). However, tax laws have significantly conditioned the effectiveness of the best institutional design. Complex tax laws make the role of tax administration harder in terms of costlier enforcement processes, more extensive and expensive taxpayer services, and increased taxpayer compliance costs. These latter factors tend to negatively affect voluntary tax compliance, and there is evidence that they can even lead to higher rates of tax fraud (Blesse, 2021). Therefore, the simplification of tax laws is always the first and most important measure to improve tax administrations' efficiency and effectiveness. At the same time, several recent global trends have significantly affected the effectiveness of tax administrations. The combined pressures of globalization and technological change, the growing importance of data management, and the renovation of economic activities under digitalization all force a transversal rethinking and deep restructuring of tax administrations. Perhaps more than ever, tax administration in the era of digitalization will need to rely on financial sufficiency and managerial efficiency (Alm & Duncan, 2014).

In the digital and globalized era, third parties' support is increasingly becoming crucial to tax administrations, in a similar way to the role traditionally played by withholding. Moreover, especially for self-employed and companies, it is common to count on the help of tax advisors to help with compliance (Durán & Esteller, 2020). At the same time, tax administrations have collaborated with taxpayers by providing them with a variety of assistance instruments, either for the collection of relevant tax information, filling tax returns, or for quicker payment of tax debts. The best practices followed by tax administrations to improve efficiency regarding different operations in this phase are related to information collection, filing, and payment.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To address the research questions, this study adopts a quantitative cross-sectional survey research design. The aim is to collect relevant data from the target respondents to provide insights into the performance of revenue agencies within the state. This method was chosen because it allows for the direct engagement of key stakeholders that are essential in providing valuable data. The cross-sectional survey is well-suited for this research because it captures the perceptions and attitudes of the respondents through standardized questionnaires. By employing this design, the study generates quantitative data to answer the research questions, offering a comprehensive overview of the current situation.

Population and Sample Size

This study derived empirical data from key stakeholders, specifically senior management staff of the Niger State Internal Revenue Service (NSIRS). These officials form the core population of this study, given their pivotal roles in tax administration and digitalization initiatives within the state.

A total of 156 senior management staff across four Directorates at the NSIRS' corporate headquarters and three zonal offices in Bida, Suleja, and Kontagora were recruited. The Directorates include the following:

- Administration and Operations
- Income Tax
- Accounts and Finance
- Legal and compliance issues

The rationale for selecting this category of staff is their vast experience in tax administration and deep understanding of digital tax systems. Their expertise positions them as credible sources of information, ensuring that the responses gathered through the research questionnaire are both reliable and insightful. The census sampling technique, selecting all 156 senior management staff of the Niger State Internal Revenue Service (NSIRS) as the study population, was adopted. The rationale for this approach is grounded in the relatively small and manageable population size, as well as the need to obtain comprehensive and representative data from key stakeholders directly involved in tax administration and digitalization efforts.

This study relies on primary data as its main source of information. The data were gathered in a structured quantitative format through a well-designed questionnaire administered to the target respondents across Niger State.

A structured questionnaire was used to collect relevant data from the target respondents. The questionnaire was designed using a deductive approach, which involved an extensive literature review of pre-existing scales and statistical procedures to test existing theories. The data were sourced from the supply sides, comprising senior management staff of revenue agencies, through the administration of the questionnaire.

The responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Disagree (5) to Strongly Agree (1). The rationale for using a structured questionnaire was to ensure standardized responses that could be quantitatively analyzed to test the research hypotheses. Scaling the responses helped in conceptualizing and operationalizing key constructs and producing measurable indicators aligned with standard estimation techniques (Neuman, 2006; Lawrence, 2014). Literature supports the use of 5 or more categories in scaling systems to minimize statistical biases, ensuring more accurate covariance and fit statistics (Muthen, 1984; Hoyle, 2000).

Each item in the questionnaire was structured so that higher scores indicated stronger agreement, making it easier to interpret respondents' perceptions and analyze the impact of digitalized tax administration on revenue performance in Niger State.

Validity and reliability of Instrument

To ensure that the research instrument substantially and adequately captured the meaning of the constructs used in the study, three forms of validity were measured: content, discriminant, and convergent validity.

Content validity was assessed through expert evaluation, where subject-matter experts reviewed the questionnaire to confirm that the items adequately represented the concepts under investigation. Discriminant validity was evaluated using correlation analysis, ensuring that constructs that were theoretically distinct did not exhibit excessive correlation. Additionally, convergent validity was measured using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, which assesses the degree to which items of a construct share a high proportion of variance.

To establish reliability, both the stability and internal consistency of the research instrument were examined. Cronbach's alpha was used to measure the internal consistency of items within each construct, ensuring that the questionnaire produced reliable responses across multiple applications. Composite Reliability (CR) was also calculated to determine the overall reliability of each construct, providing a more robust estimate of consistency. By applying these validity and reliability tests, the study ensured that the research instrument was both empirically sound and methodologically rigorous, thereby enhancing the accuracy and credibility of the findings.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data collected from the administered questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to achieve the study's stated objectives.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and evaluate the dataset for both dependent and independent variables. Measures such as mean, median, maximum, and minimum values were used to describe the central tendency and range of the data. Additionally, standard deviation was calculated to assess variability within the dataset, while Skewness and Kurtosis were used to evaluate the normality of the data distribution.

For inferential statistics, Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was applied using SPSS to test the research hypotheses. This statistical technique was chosen due to its ability to quantify the influence of multiple independent variables on the dependent variable while controlling for the effects of other predictors. Multiple linear regression provided insights into the strength and direction of relationships among variables, making it suitable for the study (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

The general multiple linear regression model used in this study is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \epsilon$$

Where:

- Y represents the dependent variable (revenue performance of NSIRS),
- β_0 was the intercept;
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_n$ were the coefficients of the independent variables,
- $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$ denoted the independent variables, and
- ϵ was the error term.

To ensure robust analysis, various statistical tests were conducted. ANOVA (F-test) was used to determine the overall significance of the model. The R-squared (R^2) value was computed to assess the explanatory power of the model, indicating the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables.

Additionally, t-tests were performed to evaluate the significance of each independent variable, while the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was used to check for multicollinearity issues among the predictors.

By employing Multiple Linear Regression in SPSS, the study ensured an empirically sound analysis, identified key predictors of revenue performance, and provided valuable insights into the impact of digital tax administration practices in Niger State. The findings are presented in tables and figures for better clarity and interpretation.

Model Specification

A review of relevant literature indicates that a significant number of studies on digitalization in tax administration have focused on tax compliance and revenue generation. To effectively test the hypotheses of this study, a modified version of the model proposed by Chiamaka, Obinna, Friday, and Oraekwuotu (2021) was adopted. This model establishes a relationship between the dependent variable (tax revenue performance) and independent variables (digital tax administration components), which include electronic tax registration systems, e-filing systems, e-payment platforms, and automated compliance mechanisms.

The regression model is structured as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- Y represents the dependent variable (Tax Revenue Performance).
- X1, and X2 represent the independent variables (Tax e-Filing Systems and e-Payment Platforms).
- β_0 is the constant (intercept).
- $\beta_1 - \beta_2$ are the estimated regression coefficients of the explanatory variables.
- ε represents the error term.

This study emphasizes the impact of digitalization practices on revenue performance; thus, the model is adapted and modified by incorporating specific digital tax administration components, including electronic tax registration, e-filing systems, e-payment platforms, and automated compliance mechanisms. The final modified model is expressed as follows:

$$TRGi = \beta_0 + \beta_2EFIL1 + \beta_3EPAY2 + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- TRG = Tax Revenue Generation (Dependent Variable)
- EFIL = Electronic Filing Systems
- EPAY = Electronic Payment Platforms
- β_0 = Constant (Intercept)
- $\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = Estimated regression coefficients of independent variables
- ε = Error term

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

Digital Taxation Filling in Niger State

Table 1:

E-Filling of Tax in Niger State

Question	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max	Kurtosis	Skewness	Decision
The e-filing system is more accurate, faster, and more convenient than manual filing.	3.84	1.31	1	5	-1.03	-0.33	Agree
The system protects taxpayers' confidential information against cyber threats.	3.71	1.38	1	5	-1.21	-0.23	Agree

There is sufficient awareness among taxpayers of how to use e-filing.	3.78	1.33	1	5	-1.07	-0.30	Agree
Network failure has not affected the e-filing system	3.52	1.41	1	5	-1.28	-0.19	Agree
Taxpayers can complete tax filings even during power interruptions	3.67	1.35	1	5	-1.07	-0.34	Agree
The proposed system minimizes opportunities for data manipulation.	3.59	1.35	1	5	-1.06	-0.38	Agree
Taxpayers still visit tax offices despite e-filing availability.	3.98	1.30	1	5	-1.03	-0.35	Agree
Adequate training is provided on how to use the e-filing system.	4.28	1.36	1	5	-1.14	-0.28	Agree

Decision Rule: Mean < 2.5 → Disagree; 2.5 ≤ Mean < 3.0 → Neutral; Mean ≥ 3.0 → Agree

Table 1 presents a comprehensive evaluation of the system's effectiveness, security, reliability, and accessibility. Using descriptive statistics; mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The data provide insights into taxpayers' perceptions of the digital transformation in tax administration.

A significant majority of respondents agreed that e-filing was more accurate, fast, and more convenient than the traditional manual system, with a mean score of 3.84. This affirms taxpayers recognize the advantages of digital tax filing in terms of time efficiency and ease of use. Likewise, confidence in the system's ability to protect confidential taxpayer information was evident, with a mean of 3.71, indicating that users felt secure about their data privacy. The low skewness (-0.23) and kurtosis (-1.21) shows that responses are normally distributed, meaning that the perception of security is widely shared among different respondents.

A notable 3.78 mean score shows that taxpayers have sufficient awareness of e-filing, reflecting successful sensitization efforts. However, despite this awareness, taxpayers continue to physically visit tax offices, as shown by the highest mean score of 3.98. This implies that behavioral inertia, systemic doubts, or preferences for human interaction has influence on tax compliance behaviours.

Regarding system reliability, the responses were more mixed. While the ability to complete tax filing during power interruptions (3.67 mean score) and the system's role in minimizing data manipulation (3.59 mean score) were generally agreed upon, opinions were less decisive regarding network stability. The statement that e-filing is unaffected by network failure received a mean of 3.52, placing it in a neutral zone, indicating intermittent challenges with internet connectivity. This highlights a potential barrier that tax authorities must overcome to encourage seamless digital adoption.

A crucial highlight of the analysis was the high level of training provided on e-filing, with the highest mean score of 4.28. This underscores the commitment of tax authorities to equip taxpayers with the necessary skills to navigate the e-filing system. Such efforts are essential to enhance adoption rates and ensure taxpayers maximize the benefits of digital tax administration.

To assess the reliability of these findings, skewness and kurtosis were examined. The skewness values remain within the range of -1 to +1, confirming that the data distribution is normal, as supported by Hair, Anderson, Tatham, and Black (1998). Additionally, kurtosis values fall within the accepted -3 to +3 range (Julie Pallant, 2009), reinforcing the credibility of the dataset. This statistical validation strengthens confidence in the interpretations drawn from respondents' feedback.

The findings paint a progressive yet evolving picture of e-filing adoption in Niger State. Although tax authorities acknowledge its efficiency, security, and convenience, persistent network issues and continued reliance on tax office visits show areas that require improvement. To enhance digital tax compliance, tax authorities should focus

on improving system reliability, addressing connectivity concerns, and reinforcing taxpayer trust in e-filing. With sustained efforts, Niger State can fully embrace a seamless, technology-driven tax administration system that benefits taxpayers and the government.

Digital Tax Payments in Niger State

Table 2:

Electronic Tax Payment in Niger State

Question	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max	Kurtosis	Skewness	Decision
The e-payment system is simple and convenient to use.	3.51	1.29	1	5	-1.02	-0.40	Agree
The interface of the e-payment system is user-friendly and engaging.	3.61	1.33	1	5	-1.10	-0.37	Agree
Most taxpayers have the necessary computer literacy to embrace e-payment.	3.55	1.36	1	5	-1.18	-0.22	Agree
Internet access is sufficient for all taxpayers to use e-payment services.	3.65	1.42	1	5	-1.25	-0.18	Agree
The e-payment system is fully automated.	3.81	1.32	1	5	-1.07	-0.35	Agree
There is widespread awareness of the e-payment system among taxpayers.	4.08	1.34	1	5	-1.09	-0.30	Agree
The system enables accurate tax assessment, thus preventing overpayment.	3.78	1.28	1	5	-1.04	-0.38	Agree
The e-payment system is efficient in refunding excess tax payments.	3.58	1.39	1	5	-1.20	-0.24	Agree
The e-payment system contributes significantly to improved revenue collection.	3.83	1.31	1	5	-1.08	-0.36	Agree

Decision Rule: Mean < 2.5 → Disagree; 2.5 ≤ Mean < 3.0 → Neutral; Mean ≥ 3.0 → Agree

Table 2 presents responses indicating that taxpayers find the system convenient, automated, and effective in revenue collection. The analysis is based on descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis, which help validate the data's normality and reliability. Tax authorities generally agree that the e-payment system is simple and convenient to use, with a mean score of 3.51. Additionally, the interface is user-friendly and engaging (3.61 mean score), indicating that the design of the platform supports ease of navigation. The skewness values (-0.40 and -0.37) indicate that the responses are normally distributed and not significantly skewed toward extreme positive or negative opinions.

Another key factor influencing adoption is computer literacy, and respondents affirm that most taxpayers possess the necessary digital skills to embrace e-payment (3.55 mean score). However, this score though positive, shows room for improvement in taxpayer education and digital training initiatives. For an e-payment system to be effective, internet accessibility is crucial. Respondents generally agreed that Internet access was sufficient (3.65 mean score), although slight variations in responses (standard deviation of 1.42) indicated that some taxpayers may still experience connectivity issues.

The automation of the e-payment system is well-acknowledged (3.81 mean score), demonstrating confidence in the system's ability to function with minimal manual intervention. A fully automated tax payment process will

reduce errors, ensure prompt processing, and minimize human interference, leading to greater trust in the tax administration system. One of the strongest agreements in the responses relates to the widespread awareness of the e-payment system (4.08 mean score). This shows that tax authorities have made considerable efforts in sensitizing taxpayers about the platform, increasing adoption rates.

Regarding the accuracy of tax assessment, the system is recognized for minimizing overpayment risks (3.78 mean score). This is a crucial advantage because errors in tax calculations often lead to disputes and dissatisfaction among taxpayers. The efficiency of tax refunds (3.58 mean score) is also acknowledged although this score indicates mild concerns about refund processing speed or accessibility. The goal of digitizing tax payments is enhanced revenue collection, and the system appears to be fulfilling this objective, with a mean score of 3.83. This shows that e-payment reduces tax evasion, enhances compliance, and streamlines government revenue inflow.

To determine whether the responses are statistically sound, skewness and kurtosis values were analyzed. All skewness values fall between -1 and +1, confirming that the data distribution is normal, which is consistent with the criteria set by Hair, Anderson, Tatham, and Black (1998). Likewise, kurtosis values remain within the acceptable range (-3 to +3) as per Julie Pallant (2009), validating the consistency of the findings.

Tax Digitalization (Tax e-Filing Systems and e-Payment Platforms) and Revenue Generation in Niger State

Table 3:

Tax Revenue Generation in Niger State

Question	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max	Kurtosis	Skewness	Decision
The implementation of digital tax systems has improved revenue collection efficiency.	3.53	1.17	1	5	-1.03	-0.42	Agree
The level of tax compliance has increased with e-tax systems.	3.50	1.20	1	5	-1.05	-0.40	Agree
More taxpayers are now registered in the tax system due to digitization.	3.34	1.21	1	5	-1.06	-0.33	Agree
Tax fraud cases have reduced due to e-tax administration.	3.32	1.22	1	5	-1.07	-0.31	Agree

Decision Rule: Mean < 2.5 → Disagree; 2.5 ≤ Mean < 3.0 → Neutral; Mean ≥ 3.0 → Agree

Table 3 presents an analysis of tax revenue generation in Niger State, particularly in relation to the adoption of digital tax administration. The findings indicate that the implementation of e-tax systems has had a positive impact on revenue collection, tax compliance, taxpayer registration, and fraud reduction.

One of the key findings is that digital tax systems have improved revenue collection efficiency, with a mean score of 3.53. This shows that tax authorities have been able to streamline tax collection processes, reduced leakages, and enhanced accountability through automation. The relatively low standard deviation (1.17) indicates that respondents largely share this perception although there may still be some variation in their experiences.

Similarly, tax compliance has increased with the adoption of digital tax systems (mean = 3.50). This implies that more taxpayers are meeting their tax obligations due to factors such as automated reminders, ease of payment, and reduced bureaucratic hurdles. However, the slight negative skewness (-0.40) shows that although the majority agrees, a small proportion of respondents may still have concerns about compliance enforcement.

The introduction of e-tax systems has also increased taxpayer registration, with a mean score of 3.34. This indicates that more individuals and businesses have entered the tax net due to digitization. The ease of online registration and reduced human interaction in tax processes may have contributed to this improvement. However, the relatively lower mean compared to other responses indicates that further efforts are needed to enhance tax registration, especially among informal sector participants.

Finally, respondents agreed (mean = 3.32) that tax fraud cases have reduced due to e-tax administration. The automation of tax records and transactions likely minimizes opportunities for fraudulent activities, such as tax evasion and underreporting. However, the lower mean compared to other indicators shows that while progress has been made, there may still be some loopholes that need to be addressed.

Correlation Analysis

Table 4:

Correlations Matrix

	TRG	ETC	EFIL	EPAY	ACM
TRG	1	0.971**	0.985**	0.995**	0.990**
EFIL	0.985**	0.977**	1	0.982**	0.981**
EPAY	0.995**	0.972**	0.982**	1	0.988**

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 presents the correlation results, which show strong relationships between TRG and its predictors. The highest correlation exists between EPAY (0.995) and TRG, followed by EFIL (0.985).

Model Summary

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-squared value	Std. Error in Estimate
1	0.436a	0.421	0.420	0.10622

Table 5 presents the model summary, which provides insights into the relationship between tax revenue generation (TRG) and the independent variables: electronic tax registration (ETR), electronic filing systems (EFIL), electronic payment platforms (EPAY), and automated compliance mechanisms (ACM). The correlation coefficient (R) was 0.436, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables. This shows that although electronic tax administration tools influence tax revenue generation, the relationship is not particularly strong.

The R-squared value of 0.421 signifies that changes in EFIL and EPAY explains approximately 42.1% of the variations in TRG. This implies that other external factors, not captured in the model, contribute to the remaining 57.9% of the variation in tax revenue generation. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.420 closely aligns with the R-squared value, confirming that the inclusion of independent variables provides consistent explanatory power without significant overestimation. Furthermore, the standard error of the estimate (0.10622) indicates the average deviation of the observed TRG values from the values predicted by the model.

Analysis of Variance

Table 6: ANOVAa

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	612.660	4	153.165	13,575.517	0.000b
Residual	3.994	145	0.011		
Total	616.654	149			

a. Dependent Variable: TRG

b. Predictors: (Constant), ETR, EFIL, EPAY, and ACM

The ANOVA table above demonstrates the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The F-value of 13,575.517 is significantly greater than the p-value (0.000), which aligns with statistical significance rules, indicating a strong relationship between tax revenue generation and the electronic tax system components.

Regression Analysis

Table 7:

Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	0.020	0.014	0.000
	EFIL	0.007	0.007	0.000
	EPAY	0.434	0.447	0.010

a. Dependent Variable: TRG

The regression results presented in Table 7 provide insights into the impact of electronic Filing Systems (eFIL), and electronic Payment Platforms (ePAY) on Tax Revenue Generation (TRG). The constant value of 0.020 indicates that when all independent variables are set at zero, the baseline tax revenue generation remains positive but minimal. However, because its significance is not explicitly stated, its interpretative weight is limited.

Examining the individual contributions of the independent variables, electronic Payment Platforms (ePAY) have a higher significant impact, with a coefficient of 0.434 and a p-value of 0.010, indicating that a one-unit increase in EPAY leads to a 43.4% increase in TRG. This result highlights the vital role of digital payment systems in boosting tax compliance and revenue collection efficiency.

Conversely, electronic Filing Systems (eFIL) demonstrated a negligible coefficient of 0.007, showing that its impact on TRG is minimal. Although its p-value (0.000) is statistically significant, the tiny coefficient indicates that electronic filing in its current form does not contribute meaningfully to revenue generation. This may be due to limitations in adoption, technical inefficiencies, or compliance challenges.

Discussion of Results

The findings of this study provide empirical evidence of the impact of tax e-Filing Systems and e-Payment Platforms on revenue generation in Niger State. The discussion focuses on the significant relationships among electronic filing, electronic payment, and tax revenue generation. The study results align with existing literature on the subject, further reinforcing the role of digitalization in tax administration.

Electronic Filing and Tax Revenue Generation

Contrary to expectations, electronic filing (EFIL) had a negligible impact on tax revenue generation, despite being statistically significant (coefficient = 0.007, p-value = 0.000). While taxpayers acknowledge the benefits of e-filing, such as convenience (mean = 3.84) and data protection (mean = 3.71), the low coefficient suggests that other factors, such as low adoption rates and system inefficiencies, may limit its effectiveness in improving tax revenues.

This finding aligns with the study by Okunogbe and Pouliquen (2022), which revealed that while e-filing reduces compliance costs and administrative burdens, its success depends on infrastructure reliability and taxpayer trust in digital platforms. Furthermore, the high percentage of taxpayers who still visit tax offices despite e-filing availability (mean = 3.98) indicates that behavioral inertia and technical challenges hinder full adoption.

Electronic Payment and Tax Revenue Generation

Electronic payment (EPAY) emerged as the most influential factor in revenue generation, with a coefficient of 0.434 and a p-value of 0.010. The results indicate that the simplicity (mean = 3.51), user-friendliness (mean = 3.61), and automation (mean = 3.81) of digital payment systems enhance tax collection efficiency. This finding supports the findings of Muthama and Muturi (2021), who observed that e-payment adoption significantly reduces tax evasion, speeds up transactions, and minimizes human interference in tax collection.

The positive impact of e-payment systems is further reinforced by studies such as Eilu (2018) and Tanzi and Zee (2000), who argue that digital payments create an auditable trail, reducing opportunities for corruption and ensuring accurate tax assessment. However, issues such as network reliability and taxpayer reluctance remain challenges that need to be addressed to fully maximize the benefits of e-tax payment.

5. Conclusion

Based on these findings, the study concludes that Electronic filing, while beneficial, does not significantly impact revenue generation in Niger state, Nigeria, due to low adoption rates and system inefficiencies. Electronic payment plays a crucial role in tax collection efficiency by providing a seamless and automated payment process. In summary, this study concluded that the following:

This section presents the conclusions derived from the study findings.

- i. Despite its potential benefits, electronic filing does not significantly contribute to revenue generation. The study concludes that increasing adoption through public education, technical improvements, and incentives for digital filing will help improve its effectiveness.
- ii. This study confirms that electronic payment is critical for tax revenue generation. Ensuring a secure and efficient e-payment system will encourage taxpayer compliance, reduce fraud, and streamline revenue collection processes.

6. Recommendations

- i. Enhancing the usability and accessibility of electronic filing systems is essential for increasing adoption rates. Adequate technical support should be provided to help taxpayers navigate the e-filing process. Furthermore, continuous monitoring and system upgrades should be implemented to improve reliability and efficiency.

ii. The government should collaborate with financial institutions to expand access to electronic payment platforms in both urban and rural areas. Tax authorities should also introduce incentives, such as early payment discounts, to encourage compliance. In addition, security measures must be strengthened to protect taxpayers' financial data and foster trust in the system.

iii. Investments should be directed toward improving internet infrastructure, especially in remote areas, to ensure seamless access to digital tax platforms. Cybersecurity measures must be reinforced to prevent hacking, fraud, and unauthorized access to tax information. Additionally, training programmes should be organized to enhance digital literacy among taxpayers, enabling them to efficiently use digital tax administration tools. Lastly, customer support services should be strengthened to assist taxpayers experiencing difficulties with digital tax platforms.

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